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Multi-Decadal Evolution of Continental Portuguese Beaches Using Landsat Satellite Imagery

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Abstract

Sandy beaches form an essential part of coastal zones as they have a key-role in the ecosystem, while providing socio-economic goods and services at the same time. Despite the ecological and social importance of these ecosystems, sandy beaches are increasingly under anthropogenic pressure. In mainland Portugal the coastal zones are one of the most populated and developed zones of the country, where, in order to adequately manage these vulnerable coastal zones, understanding of beach dynamics on various time- and spatial scales is crucial. In this MSc thesis project we used long records of freely available Landsat satellite imagery to study the evolution of beaches along the continental Portuguese coast during the last 35 years. The main objectives was to automate the process of continental Portuguese beach classification in Landsat imagery, using a machine learning random forest classifier-algorithm; and to track morphological changes of these beaches over the last decades. In total we used 8734 Landsat images to study sandy beach extent, beach, shore and coastline evolution, over seven time periods, each composed of five-year Landsat imagery. In line with previous studies we found an overall trend of decrease in beach area, from about 90 km² in 1984-89 to 65 km² in 2014-19. Furthermore we present maps showing the dynamics and change of continental Portuguese beaches, while providing qualitative information on shore and coastline evolution at the same time.

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2 Background

The MSc thesis is part of the Erasmus Mundus Marine Environment and Resources (MER Consortium) and was conducted at the University of Lisbon, under supervision of Dr. Rui Pires de Matos Taborda and Dr. Ricardo Machado Trigo. The study was conducted from January to July 2019, and was defended in September 2019 at the marine research station in Plentzia, Basque Country (Spain).

3 Introduction

Sandy beaches form an essential part of coastal zones as they have a key-role in the ecosystem, while providing socio-economic goods and services at the same time. Globally, coastal zones present a tendency to be more densely populated than the hinterland and exhibit higher rates of population growth and urbanisation (Neumann et al. [2015]). Despite the ecological and social importance of these ecosystems, coastal regions are increasingly changing under human- and climate-induced influences (Baily and Nowell [1996]). The intensive concentration of population in coastal regions is often accompanied by excessive exploitation, pollution, recreation, coastal engineering and urban development, altogether putting enormous pressure on coastal ecosystems, including sandy beaches (Defeo et al. [2009]); they may lead to biodiversity loss, habitats destruction, pollution, while conflicting as well between potential uses, and space congestion problems. At present, global climate change, with sea-level-rise in particular, added a new dimension to the yet existing anthropogenic pressures on sandy beaches (Team et al. [2014]). Sea levels have already risen through the 20th century, are expected to rise increasingly this century and therefore constitute another serious threat to stability of coastal ecosystems (Nicholls and Cazenave [2010]). It is therefore that every action affecting coastal areas should look for a balance between coastal protection, enhancement of land use and environment values (Marinho et al. [2019]). To successfully achieve the so-called integrated coastal management¹, qualitative and quantitative understanding of the coastal morphological processes, including beaches, is necessary. Observing, understanding and quantifying beaches is a precondition for a successful coastal management project because they allow for predictions about the future and therefore form the basis for coastal managers and planners who face important decisions about these vulnerable zones; it will allow to not only understand the past, but also to anticipate future.

Most of the beaches are highly dynamic systems which vary dramatically in time due to, for example, changing wave condition and human interventions; where both the modal

¹https://ec.europa.eu/environment/iczm/index_en.htm

conditions and the time variations vary spatially with environmental conditions (Wright and Short [1984]). Sandy shores and beaches can be characterized as dynamic regions that may undergo rapid advances and retreats driven by changing environmental conditions, like wave conditions, or exhibit longer-term erosion/accretion trends due to a range of factors, including an imbalance in sediment supply (Vos et al. [2019]; Wright and Short [1984]). The dynamics of these zone are driven by wind, waves and nearshore currents, which stir unconsolidated sediment and transport it seawards, landwards and alongshore, hereby continuously reshaping the topography and bathymetry of sandy coastlines (Wright and Short [1984]).

Traditionally these dynamic coastal zones have been hard to monitor since it requires time-consuming field work and/or expensive imagery stations at multiple locations (Vos et al. [2019]). It is here that Earth observation satellite data plays an increasingly important and necessary role in achieving science-supported integrated coastal management. Nowadays there are several freely available high resolution satellite data, which are at the same time becoming easier to process due to relatively new computation techniques and infrastructure. In this study we took advantage of this freely-available Landsat imagery (1984-2019) and the computational power of the Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al. [2017]) to study the evolution of continental Portuguese beaches over the last 35 years.

The main objective was to automate beach classification in Landsat imagery along the continental Portuguese coast. Furthermore the study focussed on studying the morphological change of sandy beaches by quantifying changes in sandy beach extent and qualitatively showing shore and coastline evolution, over the last 35 years, where we effectively used the previously developed classification framework. Finally the project was also intended to explore the (dis)advantages of using Google Earth Engine in studying sandy beach evolution using Landsat imagery.

The general workflow (Ch. 5) was to first generate a continuous time series consisting of seven five-year Landsat composites, from 1984 to 2019. Then we trained and deployed an Earth Engine classifier algorithm, effectively classifying these composite images, on pixel level, into water, sand, tidal-flats and other areas. Finally, these classified maps were used to quantify sandy beach extent and qualitatively track beach, shore and coastline evolution.

Thus, we produced a time series of the extent of continental Portuguese beaches using observations obtained from the Landsat archive images acquired between 1984 and 2019. The final classification results consist of 7 continental Portuguese maps of beaches at 30-m pixel resolution for set time-periods 1984-1989, 1989-1994, 1994-1999, 1999-2004, 2004-2009, 2009-2014, and 2014-2019; a map which shows sand gains and losses between the first and last time period respectively; and resampled (5m) beach polygons, representing the shore

and coastline.

The framework to automate beach classification in Landsat imagery is openly available, under MIT license, in this GitHub repository: <https://github.com/florisrc/thesis>. All developed maps are openly available as Earth Engine assets (App. D) and most of them can be explored in the Continental Portuguese Beach Change Explorer (<https://florisrc.users.earthengine.app/view/ee-app-portuguese-beaches-v6>).

3.1 The coastal zone and its monitoring

The coastal zone can be described as the interface between land and sea, where land is affected by its proximity to the sea due to the influence of marine processes, while the part of the sea is affected by its proximity to land due to influence of terrestrial processes (Masselink and Hughes [2014]). These coastal zones are dynamic geomorphological by nature and respond on different temporal and spatial scales to changes in natural and anthropogenic effects. Wave action, winds, tides, and surges affect the coastal zone naturally, while man-made effects result from resource exploitation, construction, and pollution.

The coastal zone is composed of several zones, although the boundaries between these zones are often not yet clearly defined (Carapuço et al. [2016]). Therefore we will here stipulate how we define the boundaries which are relevant for this study. Following Carapuço et al. [2016] the coastline position refers to the landward limit of the backshore; the boundary between foredune-toe, cliff, or structure confining the beach. The shoreline generally refers to the physical interface of land and water; it was defined by Carapuço et al. [2016] at several levels, but in this study the shoreline is to be understood as the dry- and wet beach boundary at intermediate tidal level. Either shore and coastline are thus defined upon visibly discernible features (Vos et al. [2019]), *i.e.* the instantaneous water and vegetation line, in five-year composites. Beaches are then defined as the unconsolidated sandy parts of the coastal zone, located between the shore and coastline.

There are several methods to monitor sandy beaches, and shore and coastlines. In-situ field studies, usually performed with GPS surveying techniques, provide highly accurate data (*i.e.*, sub-meter accuracy) but are often limited in spatial extent and temporal resolution as they depend on human operators (Vos et al. [2019]) and require accessible environments. Over the past several decades coastal video monitoring systems became increasingly used and have proven to be an invaluable tool for remote sensing of the coastal environment, including sandy beaches. Video imagery has been used to study coastal morphological change, surf zone hydrodynamics, beach attendance and safety, and also to detect marine debris (Dusek et al. [2019]). Although fixed position cameras have been used for scientific

purposes since 1980s (Dusek et al. [2019]), their use steadily increased since the early nineties, after Lippmann and Holman [1989] discovered that ten-minute time-exposure (timex) images are very useful in locating submerged sand bars and rip channels. Since then the beach is at an increasing amount of places being monitored by Argus video monitoring systems (Coastal Imaging Lab) (Román-Rivera and Ellis [2018]). However, nowadays there exist several other video monitoring systems, with also more diverse applications, *e.g.*, COSMOS (Taborda and Silva [2012]) and WebCAT (Dusek et al. [2019]). Despite all international effort spatial coverage of video monitoring systems is still limited because fixed cameras require a high vantage point, power supply, maintenance and they cannot operate in areas where infrastructure is not available (Vos et al. [2019]). It is due to this constraint in spatial coverage that they are not useful to study morphological beach, shore and coastal change on larger spatial scales (meso- to macro scale).

To study morphological beach, shore and coastline change over spatially larger areas (meso- to macro scale), aerial photographs have been used, for example, by Ponte Lira et al. [2016]. Aerial photographs have been taken since 1900s, can generally be obtained with minimal interference to the environment and require less logistical efforts compared to field experiments, while also providing spatially larger opportunities (Román-Rivera and Ellis [2018]). However, manned aircraft overflights can become costly, especially when multi-temporal aerial photographs over vast areas are required. It probably is therefore that unfortunately most countries did not acquire aerial imagery at high temporal frequency.

During last years, high resolution satellite images begun to be regarded as a competitive alternative of aerial photography. Both their scale and operational conditions still had to meet the standards of aerial photographs, but recently some important steps have been made. Satellite observations provide are a rich source of multispectral imagery for morphological beach, shore and coastline change analysis because of their extensive spatial coverage, reliable revisit time and long-term historical datasets. Nowadays there is an immense amount of satellite data, freely-accessible to the public (Zhu et al. [2019]) through the convenient and computationally powerful Google Earth Engine platform (Gorelick et al. [2017]).

3.2 Growing importance of satellite imagery

Just more than two decades ago, in 1996, Baily and Nowell noted that new techniques such as satellite imagery are often financially too demanding. Nowadays however, satellites have become increasingly important in studying Earth: they are deployed for a wide range of commercial and scientific applications, like inferring chlorophyll concentrations in the

ocean, or to study and forecast malaria (Rogers et al. [2002]). More recently Yang et al. pointed out how satellite remote sensing has provided major advances in understanding the climate system and its changes by quantifying processes and spatio-temporal states of the atmosphere, land and oceans ([Yang et al., 2013]).

Whereas long-term coastal zone monitoring programs, like Argus, are scarce and limited in spatial coverage (Harley et al. [2015]), availability of satellite data provides the opportunity to analyse more than 30 years of imagery with global coverage (Vos et al. [2019]). Satellite remote sensing can provide, at increasingly higher resolution, cost-effective long-term coastal zone data, which is particularly useful for long term studies and at sites where in-situ field measurements are difficult, or not even possible. Nowadays satellite imagery spanning more than 35 years is publicly and freely available, altogether forming a rich source of long-term historical coastal zone datasets, suitable to extract repeated information, across spatial scales ranging from localised studies to unprecedented global applications (Vos et al. [2019]; Zhu et al. [2019]).

Huang et al. [2018] provides an overview of satellites which are commonly used in surface water extraction (App. A.1). However, this table may also explain why Landsat imagery is so widely used in studying the coastal zone. Starting the with launch of Landsat-1 in 1972, the Landsat program currently has the longest running terrestrial satellite record and is therefore exceptionally useful for studying the coastal zone on a large scale (meso- to macro scale) and a multi-decadal timescale (App. A). During many years Landsat data had to be bought from the USGS, but since 2008 this institute adopted a free and open Landsat data policy (Woodcock et al. [2008]). This change in policy led to a substantial increase in use of Landsat data, greatly benefiting scientific research, operational applications and has therefore contributed to many segments of society ([Zhu et al., 2019]). Landsat data was for instance used to globally map annual forest change ([Hansen et al., 2013]); while Donchyts et al. [2016] used it to map the extent of Earth’s surface waters; Lujendijk et al. [2018] used it to study the state of the world’s beaches; and, recently Murray et al. [2019] used it to map the global distribution and trajectory of tidal flats.

For decades, the approach to work with satellite data was to first download the data to your personal computer/network and then process them according to your needs. Recently however, there has been a major advancement in data storage and processing: instead of doing all the work in a local environment, it is now possibly to store and process data in the cloud, *i.e.* the job is divided between thousands of computers located in multiple server centres. All of the previously mentioned geospatial mapping studies greatly benefited from this relatively new approach, which easily accessible through the Google Earth Engine. This Earth Engine is a cloud-based platform for planetary-scale geospatial analysis that brings

Google’s massive computational capabilities easily controlled through an Internet-accessible application programming interface (API) and an associated web-based interactive development environment (IDE) that enables rapid prototyping and visualization of results(Gorelick et al. [2017]).

3.3 Study area

The study was performed along the continental coastal zone of Portugal. The continental mainland of Portugal is located in the south west part of Europe at the western sector of Iberian Peninsula (Fig. 1). The coastline of continental Portugal is bordered by the Atlantic Ocean and extends for about 987 km from south of the Minho River in northern Portugal to west of the Guadiana river mouth in southern Portugal (Andrade et al. [2002]). The coastal zone includes a wide range of morpho-sedimentary environments, such as beaches, cliffs, estuaries, lagoons and barrier islands Ponte Lira et al. [2016].

The wave climate is highly energetic, but the amount of wave energy varies strongly between western and southern parts of the coast; the western facing coastal stretches are fully exposed to the dominant NW high-energy swells, while the south-facing parts are sheltered and therefore characterized by a milder wave regime (Ponte Lira et al. [2016]). However, where the northern areas of Portugal are predominantly exposed to the high wave conditions from NW and W directions, the south areas are also influenced from the W and SW storms. Marraccini [2015] found that the inter-annual variability of winter wave characteristics is associated, to large extent, with indices of a few large-scale atmospheric circulation modes, such as the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and Eastern Atlantic (EA) climate mode.

Tides along the continental Portuguese coast are semi-diurnal and meso-tidal, ranging from 2 to 4m during spring tides, and the mean sea level is +2 m chart datum (CD) (Coelho et al. [2009]). Tides are considered to be unimportant to coastal processes except in the vicinity of inlets and tide-dominant basins. However, the strong wave regime is considered to induce a southward alongshore transport of $1-2 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$ (Coelho et al. [2009]).

During the last few decades anthropogenic influences have become increasingly important in structuring the coastal zone of Continental Portugal. Since 1950s man implemented several coastal structures, like groynes and seawalls, while alluvial sources progressively weakened due to, for example, the creation of reservoirs; nowadays, up to 80% of sediments that could have been transported in natural condition are being retained due to these weakened alluvial conditions (Marinho et al. [2018]; Pinto et al. [2017]). The coastal interventions along the continental Portuguese coast since the 1950s included both beach nourishment and

implementation of man-made structures. Notable places of beach nourishment are north of Porto near Matosinhos, South of Aveiro, Costa Caparica, Rio Arade and Rio Formosa (Pinto et al. [2017]). The number of beach nourishments steeply increased between time periods 1980-1989 and 1990-1999, from 5 to 35 respectively (Pinto et al. [2017]). This increment coincides with a paradigm shift of hard coastal measures (implementation of man-made structures) to soft coastal measures (for example, beach nourishment) in coastal management; where there were 71 hard structures implemented during 1980-1990, having decreased to just 21 between 1990-2000.

Nowadays beach evolution in continental Portugal is mainly conditioned by its energetic wave climate, the man-made structures and the progressive weakening of the alluvial sources. Ponte Lira et al. [2016] calculated that along all the beach-dune systems of Continental Portugal beach erosion has been the dominant trend during the last 50 years, with a mean change rate of 0.24 ± 0.01 m year⁻¹. Nevertheless they also noted that although erosion is dominant, evolution is variable in signal and magnitude for different areas along the coast. According to their study, most problematic beach erosion issues were found in the coastal stretches of Espinho-Torreira and Costa Nova-Praia de Mira, Cova da Gala-Leirosa, and Cova do Vapor-Costa da Caparica.

3.4 Research objectives

The main object of this project is to investigate the extent to which the geometry of continental Portuguese beaches can be classified in freely available Landsat imagery in an automated manner, using parallel computation techniques of Google Earth Engine. Next the study focusses on how the continental Portuguese beaches evolved over the last 35 years by comparing their extent and tracking beach, shore and coastline evolution over seven composites, each consisting of five years Landsat imagery. Finally the project also aims to explore the (dis)advantages of Google Earth Engine when studying sandy beach evolution using Landsat imagery.

3.5 Structure of the thesis

The thesis is structured following a common thread. First, chapter 4 provides a general background on beach monitoring using imagery; the Landsat project, its imagery and dataset; the Google Earth Engine; spectral indices; and image classification. Next, chapter 5 covers detailed descriptions of pre-processing, processing and post-processing of the dataset. Chapter 6 presents and evaluates the main results of this study. Subsequently these results are further discussed in chapter 7. This chapter concludes with the most important findings

Figure 1: Study area visualized as true colour composite on top of a Natural Earth basemap.

of the study. Finally chapter 8 presents recommendations for future work.

The framework to automate beach classification of continental Portuguese beaches in Landsat imagery, developed during this thesis, is openly available, under MIT license, in this GitHub repository: <https://github.com/florisrc/thesis>. All constructed maps are openly available as Earth Engine assets (App. D). Finally, most of the constructed maps can be explored in the Continental Portuguese Beach Change Explorer.²

4 Scientific background and data

This chapter provides scientific background of the thesis: it summarizes beach monitoring using satellite imagery, describes the data and details some of the computations which were used in the study. Furthermore, it describes the basic functionality of the Google Earth Engine (GEE), as it is the main platform used in the study. This chapter can be understood as the base for understanding the methodology which was used in this study.

²<https://florisrc.users.earthengine.app/view/ee-app-portuguese-beaches-v6>

4.1 Beach monitoring using imagery

At present there are two methods to extract coastal zone information from remote sensing images: visual interpretation and automated extraction. Ponte Lira et al. [2016] used visual interpretation to classify aerial images of beaches along Continental Portugal. Such approach is simple and has high accuracy, but because of its slow speed and heavy workload, it cannot provide rapid data over a large area. Compared with visual interpretation, automatic interpretation is faster and more efficient, but suffers from spectral confusion and error, wherefore it usually requires complex post-processing operations (Chen et al. [2019]). Several authors have used automated classification, in form of pixel-based supervised classification, and edge detection to quantify the state of Earth’s surface waters and beaches respectively ([Donchyts et al., 2016]; [Luijendijk et al., 2018]).

The main approaches in automatic interpretation of coastal zone information from remote sensing imagery include: 1) edge detection-based method; 2) index analysis-based method; 3) threshold segmentation-based method; 4) region growing-based method; 5) neural network-based method; 6) and, sub-pixel method ([Chen et al., 2019]). Firstly, edges can be automatically detected by discontinuities in brightness: high gradients in brightness at edges will stand out against uniform parts of the image, with low gradients in brightness. Secondly, images can be interpreted automatically by index based methods, which exploits contrasting aspects of certain wavelengths with respect to, for instance, land and water (see more section 4.4). Thirdly, images can be clustered into parts with similar spectral properties using specified thresholds. Fourthly, the region growing based method clusters pixels with similar spectral properties and hereby provides more accurate classification data (Chen et al. [2019]). Fifthly, coastal imagery can be classified by using neural networks, which learn to distinguish certain features by a feedback loop on sample data. Lastly, the sub-pixel method is found upon the different responses of water and land in multi-spectral bands. Sub-pixel methods exploit the spectral information of the image; it contains information about the different spectra (and so classes) within each pixel: a pixel containing pure seawater will have a different spectrum with respect to a pixel containing a mixture of sand and water. The final classification uses this approach and can be understood as expressing the probability that a certain pixel has a that class. To the contrary object oriented classification are based on supra-pixel analysis. This approach considers the pixel spectrum, its relative spatial location, and the local spectral homogeneity and shape of adjacent cluster of similar pixels.

Within this context, Vos et al. recently managed to automate the process of shoreline extraction (CoastSat; <https://github.com/kvos/CoastSat>) in satellite imagery available in

the Google Earth Engine platform ([Vos et al., 2019]). The tool uses a subpixel image classification method, incorporating a thresholded Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) to derive the instantaneous satellite derived shoreline positions. In this process there are three main steps: image classification, sub-pixel shoreline detection and tidal correction. Image classification uses spectral information captured in each image to classify each pixel in the image into four classes of sand, water, swash or other. Then, when the instantaneous shoreline is detected, the horizontal position is tidally corrected to the 0.7 m contour using an assumed average beach slope.

Another recent example of automated beach analysis is Luijendijk et al. [2018] study to the state of world’s beaches ([Luijendijk et al., 2018]). In that study, they applied supervised (human-guided) classification to global cloud-free satellite images to identify sandy beaches on a global level. Next they used a canny edge detection filter to roughly estimate the position of the shoreline in 33 one-year Landsat composites. Having placed cross-shore transects, at 250-m interval on a global level, they were able to calculate the shoreline change rate at transects which were, according to the previously performed classification, identified as beaches.

Either of these studies incorporate both classification and thresholding algorithms to extract shorelines. However, whereas Luijendijk et al. [2018] used this classification to identify beaches where shoreline change rates would be calculated, Vos et al. [2019] used classification to improve performance of his thresholding algorithm. In this study however, we were primarily concerned with mapping sandy beaches, to their full extent, from shore to coastline. Due to the scope of this project, it was decided to directly deduce shorelines from the classification results, instead of also implementing a thresholding algorithm to extract shorelines.

CoastSat is particularly effective in detecting shorelines in individual satellite images. Here we are concerned with multi-annual composites, which are, so far are difficult to ingest into Vos et al.’s CoastSat-tool. With respect to Luijendijk et al. [2018]’s study, initial exploration of the Landsat data set showed that cloud-free annual composites often do not contain enough images to sustain an image in which analysis of morphological sandy beach, shore and coastline change is possible. This problem was already acknowledged by Luijendijk et al. [2018] themselves, but since they applied their study on a global level, resolution of annual composites was still found acceptable.

4.2 Landsat project

The Landsat program, jointly led by NASA and USGS, has provided near-continuous observation of Earth’s surface since 1972 (App. A.2).³ The mission started with the launch of the Earth Resources Technology Satellite (ERTS-1) in 1972. Later this satellite was renamed Landsat-1 and its successors Landsat-2, Landsat-3 and Landsat-4 were launched within one decade, in 1975, 1978 and 1982 respectively. Landsat-5 was launched in 1984 and surprisingly acquired global data for 28 years and 10 months. On the contrary, Landsat-6 never acquired any useful data because it failed to reach its orbit in 1993. Landsat-7 and Landsat-8 have been launched in 1999 and 2013 respectively, and currently both continue to acquire data. The project is guaranteed to be maintained in the coming years as Landsat-9 is being developed and should be launched by the end of 2020.

The long running record of the Landsat program and its global coverage make the data exceptionally useful for large scale studies on multi-annual to multi-decadal time frame. Since 2008 this data has been freely available, and most likely because of this no-cost availability it has been increasingly used in scientific research (Zhu et al. [2019]). This is also highlighted by numerous high-impact studies in recent years (Ch. 3).

4.2.1 Technical details

The initial Landsat sensors were developed including four broad bands, but over time the band ranges became increasingly narrow, numerous and more positioned at certain wavelength ranges (Wulder et al. [2019]). The initial Landsat-1 Multispectral Scanner System (MSS) had spectral bands that occupied visible and near infrared wavelengths and were collecting data that was typically resampled to 60m a 6-bit quantization (Wulder et al. [2019]). The next generations, Landsat-2 and Landsat-3 followed a similar MSS configuration. The following Landsat-4 and Landsat-5 carried a Thematic Mapper (TM) sensor, occupied 7 spectral bands at 8-bit quantization, with a higher resolution (30m) and introduced two short wave infrared bands (SWIR) (Wulder et al. [2019]). Landsat-7 saw carried the Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+), which generally has spectral and spatial resolution characteristics as its predecessor, but additionally contained a 15-m spatial resolution panchromatical channel and increased TIR band resolution (Wulder et al. [2019]). Finally, Landsat-8 carries an Operational Land Imager, which has refined spectral band passes and contains two additional channels, a coastal aerosol and a cirrus channel, which are respectively meant to provide additional information for aquatic sciences and improve cloud detection and screening, with 12-bit quantization (Wulder et al. [2019]). Beyond these

³<https://landsat.gsfc.nasa.gov/>

sensor improvements there have been advances in the satellites, detectors, communications, downlink capacity, and ground system technology (Wulder et al. [2019]).

The Quality Assessment (QA) band consists of several bit-packed combinations that represent information about surface, atmosphere and sensor conditions that can affect the overall usefulness of a given pixel within a scene (Wulder et al. [2019]). This band allows to improve integrity of the study by indicating which pixels might be affected by artificial artefacts or cloud contamination. When such pixels are included in a study, the higher level processed data will not resemble the true spectral characteristics of that land cover.

4.3 Google Earth Engine

In December 2010 Google launched the Google Earth Engine (GEE), an advanced cloud-based geospatial processing platform, designed mainly for planetary-scale environmental data analysis (Gorelick et al. [2017]). Since then the platform has been increasingly used, especially in developing countries (Kumar and Mutanga [2018]), and formed the basis for various high-impact publications (Ch. 3). It differentiates itself from Google Earth by its ability to analyse and manipulate data according to users needs. It combines a multi-petabyte catalogue of satellite imagery and geospatial datasets, which allow users to visualize, manipulate, edit and create spatial data in an easy and fast way (App. B.1). Furthermore it incorporates a wide range of spatial manipulation tools which allows scientists, researchers, and developers to detect changes, map trends, and quantify differences on the Earths surface. Next, the Earth Engine API also contains a library of operators which allow users to interact with Earth Engine’s data and use its processing system that automatically subdivides and distributes computations, providing high-throughput analysis capabilities (Gorelick et al. [2017]). Users can use the Earth Engine after signing up at <https://earthengine.google.com>.

4.3.1 Client versus cloud-based

Earth Engine opened a new big data paradigm for storage and analysis of remote sensed data at a scale that was not feasible using desktop processing machines. Essentially this progress was made possible by a fundamentally different approach in data processing. Traditionally data were stored and processed on a personal/network level environment, which would also define the limits of processing power and storage capacity. However, in cloud computing, the aim is to shift everything to the cloud so that users can access the data remotely without being physically present at a specific place. Simply put, cloud computing is the delivery of computing servicerservers, storage, databases, networking, software, analytics

and more, over the Internet (the cloud). As a result data processing and storage are with cloud computing convenient and more efficient than ever.

Due to this duality between personal/network and cloud environment, it is important to distinguish between Earth Engine objects and other objects or primitives that might be in your code when working with Earth Engine ([Gorelick et al., 2017]). The Earth Engine objects can be recognized by starting with *ee.* and are handled by manipulating client-side proxy objects in your script. The proxy object does not contain any data and is just a handle for objects on the server; the local programming environment (*e.g.*, a Python script) is not performing any of the computation itself. The entire chain of operations is written by client-side proxy objects and sent to the server for execution, but this means that it is not possible to mix Earth Engine library calls with standard local processing idioms. For example, when *getInfo()* is called, Earth Engine will open the container and determine what is inside, but it will block the rest of the code until that is done. Similarly JavaScript/Python functionality such as conditionals and for-loops are recommended not to be used; the client does not know what is in the server-side *ee.Thing* and will start synchronous calls to *getInfo()*, blocking the rest of code. To use Earth Engine to its full extent and benefit from its processing power, server object and functions, easily recognizable by starting with *ee.Thing*, should be used, because it is inefficient or illogical to mix client and server objects.

4.3.2 Google Earth Engine Data

The Earth Engine data catalogue is composed of various widely used publicly available geospatial datasets, including satellite and aerial imaging systems in both optical and non-optical wavelengths, environmental variables, weather and climate forecasts and hindcasts, land cover, topographic and socio-economic datasets (Gorelick et al. [2017]). All this data is preprocessed to a level which allows efficient access, while information is preserved, and removes many barriers associated with data management.

The raw scenes in Earth Engine contain imagery with digital numbers (DNs) that represent scaled radiance. The conversion of DN to at-sensor radiance is a linear transformation, for which the coefficients can be found in the image's metadata. Conversion from raw scenes to surface reflectance generally requires some sort of atmospheric correction, which corrects for instance the scattering and absorption effects from the atmosphere. The corrected surface reflectance images are readily available in Earth Engine's data catalogue.

In Earth Engine, related images, for instance the ones produced by a single sensor, are grouped together and presented as a collection. Collections are organised in such way that they allow for fast filtering and sorting capabilities, which makes it easy for users to search through millions of individual images to select data that meets specific spatial, temporal or

other criteria.

4.3.3 Python API and JavaScript Cloud Editor

The Earth Engine API is available in Python and JavaScript, either of them having advantages and caveats. Furthermore, the Python API can either be run as a Datalab Docker container on a Google Cloud Platform, Docker container on a local computer or simply installed as the Earth Engine Python Library.

The Earth Engine code editor is a web-based JavaScript IDE that allows fast, interactive algorithm development; its features are specifically designed to facilitate fast and easy development of complex geospatial workflows (Gorelick et al. [2017]).

The minimal Python API installation maximizes flexibility in customizing your Python environment, but a higher level of technical skill may be required to create a working environment. Google also warns that given the differences between operating systems, Python installation methods and library versions, it may be difficult for others to reproduce your environment, which eventually may limit collaboration opportunities and make getting support more difficult.⁴ Nevertheless the Python API is extremely powerful for developers who want full control over their development environment. Unfortunately map output is currently not supported in the Python API.

In this project it was generally found most efficient to "play around" in the JavaScript IDE, but to develop the final framework in the Python API. Working with the Python API keeps projects well structured, while allowing batch exporting in large quantities and straightforward GIT integration.

4.3.4 Toolbox

Earth Engine provides several built in functions, like supervised classifications, principal component analysis, interpolation and segmentation algorithms. Furthermore the Earth Engine API includes several algorithms to correct, for example, atmospheric contamination and mask out clouds. Recently some of Earth Engine's capabilities may were made available to be integrated into a TensorFlow deep learning environment. The Earth Engine TensorFlow integration may be extremely powerful when it comes to tracking certain moving objects, *i.e.*, tidal-ebb bars. In addition, Earth Engine developers team recently also introduced some new segmentation algorithms, like SNIC (Achanta and Susstrunk [2017]), which can be expected to contribute to improved land-use classifications.

⁴https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/python_install

4.3.5 Limitations and restrictions

Earth Engine currently has user quota on concurrent queries to prevent errant or resource-intensive scripts from negatively impacting the availability of the service. These limits are separated for computation requests (*i.e.*, requests with paths that begin with /api/) and map tile requests (*i.e.*, requests with paths that begin with /map/). Google is allowing only a certain amount of queries per second, while client-side computations will time-out after a few minutes and exports are also restricted to some extent. Earth Engine's limits should especially be taken into account with on-demand computation. On-demand tasks are seen interactively, in the JavaScript IDE. Most of the on-demand limits can be avoided by batch-processing, *i.e.*, trigger an export to Earth Engine assets, Google Cloud or Google drive. In addition it was noted also some of the processing time-out and memory capacity errors can be avoided by batch exporting intermediary results; for example, export classification results as assets prior to post-classification change analysis. Memory limit errors will typically arise when operations are applied to spatially large images, image or feature collections. Likewise console printout of feature and image collections is limited to 5000 elements. Often these limitations can easily be avoided by filtering the collection and hence considering less than 5000 elements. Also storage capacities, to save results, in Google Drive and Google Cloud are limited, currently to 15Gb free storage. At this moment using Earth Engine TensorFlow integration requires use of Google Cloud buckets. Although these buckets are initially free to use, they require sign up with credit card details. In this study, using cloud buckets decelerated the workflow whilst also adding an extra layer of complexity in the data structure.

Nevertheless there is the possibility to ask Google for extra computational power when a project promises to have extraordinary results. In general the platform is built to encourage an interactive and iterative mode of data exploration and algorithm development. Once the user is satisfied with the algorithm, it is recommended to submit a batch-processing request to Earth Engine to compute the result at full scale and materialize it either as an image in Earth Engine or as one or more image, table, or video files for download (Gorelick et al. [2017]).

4.4 Spectral indices

Spectral indices are combinations of spectral reflectance from two or more wavelengths that indicate the relative abundance of features of interest. Vegetation indices are the most popular type, but other indices are available for burned areas, man-made (built-up) features, water, and geologic features.

For shoreline detection application, the the relevant spectral bands are the visible bands (blue, green,red), the near-infrared band (NIR) and the short-wave infrared band (SWIR1) (Vos et al. [2019]). Water and wet surfaces characteristically show strong absorption in the near infrared (NIR) and shortwave infrared (SWIR) spectrum, while dry soils and vegetation are highly reflecting radiation in these spectral ranges. Therefore, these spectral bands and indices derived thereof have a high potential for measuring moisture levels in soils and vegetation and are now widely used indicators for water body delineation and wetland mapping. More specifically, considering multispectral imagery the normalized water index (NDWI; Eq. 1) is often calculated to enhance water areas, while suppressing the green and soil areas (Li et al. [2018]). This well-established index measures the difference between green and infrared reflectance and normalizes the value by the sum of the two reflectance's. Using these bands for classification is also advantageous, since radiation in this spectral range is usually less affected by atmospheric aerosol scattering than the visible spectral region (McFeeters [1996]). Afterwards this index was modified by Xu [2006] by substituting the NIR band with the shortwave infrared 1 (SWIR1) band, and calling it the modified Normalized Difference Water Index (mNDWI; Eq. 2). According to Xu [2006] this modification considerably improves the detectability of open water bodies and reduces confusion with built-up areas. In addition Feyisa et al. [2014] developed the Automated Water Extraction Index (AWEI; Eq. 3) for Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM) bands, to maximize the separability of water and non-water land cover classes using a steady threshold of zero and is especially targeted at improving the separability of water and shadows. Finally the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI; Eq. 4) quantifies vegetation by measuring the difference between near-infrared, which is strongly reflected by vegetation, and red light, which is absorbed by vegetation ([Kriegler et al., 1969]). Essentially all these indices provide are probability-based proxies about how much water/vegetation is contained in a single pixel.

$$NDWI = \frac{\rho_{green} - \rho_{NIR}}{\rho_{green} + \rho_{NIR}} \quad (1)$$

$$mNDWI = \frac{\rho_{green} - \rho_{SWIR1}}{\rho_{green} + \rho_{SWIR1}} \quad (2)$$

$$AWEI = 4 * (\rho_{green} - \rho_{SWIR1}) - (0.25 * \rho_{NIR} + 2.75 * \rho_{SWIR2}) \quad (3)$$

$$NDVI = \frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{red}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{red}} \quad (4)$$

where ρ_{blue} , ρ_{green} , ρ_{red} , ρ_{nir} and ρ_{swir} are blue (450520 nm), green (520600 nm), red (630690 nm), near-infrared (NIR: 760900 nm), shortwave infrared 1 (SWIR1: 1550 -

51660 nm), and shortwave infrared 2 (SWIR2: 2100 - 2300 nm) bands of Landsat TM/ETM+/OLI imagery, respectively.

4.5 Image classification

Land cover classification of remote sensing imagery is a task which falls into the general category of pattern recognition (Canty [2019]). These pattern recognition problems are usually approached by developing appropriate machine learning algorithms. Here, machine learning roughly involves tasks for which there is no known direct method to compute a desired output from a set of inputs. The machine learning algorithms can either classify images unsupervised or supervised ([Canty, 2019]). In unsupervised classification machine learning algorithms will cluster the input data into certain categories without any assistance of labelled training data. In supervised classification there is always reference being made to a subset of labelled training data. The strategy adopted is for the computer to learn from a set of representative examples; the algorithm is trained to associate certain patterns with a certain class. In the case of supervised classification, the task can often be seen as one of modelling probability distributions.

In this study we applied supervised classification. There are several supervised machine learning algorithms, *e.g.*, CART (Breiman et al. [1984]), random forest (Breiman [2001]) and XGBoost (Chen and Guestrin [2016]), but not all are included in the Earth Engine API. The random forest algorithm has proved to be extremely successful in land cover classifications (*e.g.*, Hansen et al. [2013] and Murray et al. [2019]). However, nowadays the XGBoost algorithm appears to outperform random forest, by being the winning solution of most machine learning competitions (Georganos et al. [2018]), but unfortunately the XGBoost algorithm is not readily available in Earth Engine yet. With respect to coastal ecosystem classification, supervised classification effectively uses a wide range of spectral and physical covariates that are informative of pixel-scale tidal inundation dynamics in the coastal zone.

5 Methodology

This chapter covers detailed descriptions of the approach which was used to automate continental Portuguese beach classification in Landsat imagery and track its changes over the period 1984 - 2019. First subsection 5.1 describes how the Landsat imagery collection was created, and subsection 5.2 elaborates on how this imagery collection was processed. Next, subsection 5.3 provides details about the classification of these Landsat composites, explaining also the process of training a classifier algorithm. Subsequently, subsection 5.4 points

out how the classified images were further processed to optimize results. Then subsection 5.5 describes out how the classifications were used to study beach evolution over time. Finally, subsection 5.6 provides some details about the limitations and uncertainties of the used methodology.

The general workflow was to generate a continuous time series consisting of seven five-year Landsat composites, from 1984 to 2019; train and deploy an Earth Engine classifier algorithm, which demarcated water, beaches, tidal flats and other areas, on pixel level, in these composites; to analyse the changes in beach area over time; and to finalize the results with use of some additional third party software (Fig. 2).

Thus, we produced a time series of the extent of continental Portuguese beaches using observations obtained from the Landsat archive images acquired between 1984 and 2019. The final classification results consist of 7 continental Portuguese maps of beaches at 30-m pixel resolution for set time-periods 1984-1989, 1989-1994, 1994-1999, 1999-2004, 2004-2009, 2009-2014, and 2014-2019; a map which shows sand gains and losses between the first and last time period respectively; and seven maps consisting of beach polygons, resampled to about 5-m pixel resolution, representing the shore and coastline.

5.1 Landsat collection

The Landsat dataset is composed of the atmospherically corrected surface reflectance from the Landsat 4, 5, 7, 8 TM/ ETM+/OLI sensors, readily available in Earth Engine’s data catalogue. These collections were filtered according to date, creating a continuous time series of seven five-year composites from 01/01/1984 to 01/01/2019. It was decided to use five-year composites since this would average out seasonal variability in wave and beach characteristics, the tidal stage, while containing sufficient imagery to sustain an image in which analysis of morphological sandy beach, shore and coastline change is possible. Hence, we created seven stacks of images, each consisting of five years Landsat imagery. For all these seven image stacks clouds were masked at medium confidence level using Landsat’s Quality Assessment (QA) band (Li et al. [2019]). Next, the green, shortwave infrared 1 and 2, near infrared and red bands were extracted from all non-cloudy images renamed. Finally all Landsat imagery present in each of the stacks was merged into one collection. So finally we obtained a successive time series of seven non-cloudy 5-year Landsat imagery collections from 1984 to 2019 (Fig. 3).

Figure 3 shows the amount of images that were included in each of the seven image stacks. In total 8734 images were analysed for this study. The figure also shows that there is an increasing trend in available Landsat images from 1984 to 2019 due to the fact that

Figure 2: Workflow diagram showing the step-by-step procedure to map continental Portuguese beaches, shore and coastlines, calculate beach extent and map beach changes between time-periods.

Figure 3: The number of Landsat archive images used to map continental Portuguese beaches for each time period in our analysis. The total number of Landsat images used in the random-forest classification was 8734.

revisit time of Landsat-8 is shorter, while at the same time Landsat-7 is still operating until present.

5.2 Processing

For all images in each of the seven image-stacks several spectral indices (NDVI, NDWI, mNDWI and AWEI) were calculated by mapping (in parallel computing sense) Earth Engines built in function *thing.normalizedDifference* over the collection using equation 1, 2, 3, 4. Subsequently a combined reducer was applied to calculate a wide range of descriptive statistics for each of these spectral indices. In Earth Engine, reducers are used to aggregate data over time, space, bands, arrays and other data structures. In this project we followed Murray et al. [2019] and applied a combined reducer, consisting of *min()*, *max()*,

Table 1: Predictor data layers used by the random-forest classifier to classify pixels as water, sand, tidal-flat or other

Dataset	Spec. ind./bands	Reducer	Number of pred. var.
Landsat SR (4,5,7,8)	NDWI, mNDWI, AWEI	min	3
		max	3
		median	3
		stdDev	3
		percentile(10, 25, 50, 75, 90)	15
		intervalMn((0-10):(10-25):(10-90):(25-50));	12
		intervalMn((25-75):(50-75):(75-90):(90-100))	12
	NDVI, nir, swir1	intervalMn(10-90)	3
ETOPO1 Global Relief Model			1
Global surface water occurrence			1
Total			56

median(), *stdDev()*, *percentile[10, 25, 50, 75, 90]* and several *intervalMeans(x, y)* to all NDWI, mNDWI and AWEI values in each of the image stacks. In addition, still following Murray et al., we aggregated NDVI values using an *intervalMean(10, 90)* reducer. Hence we obtained 54 different bands, each representing one of the spectral index predictor variables. Finally these bands (hereafter: predictor variables) were merged into one image, while also adding a Digital Elevation Model (NOAA/NGDC/ETOPO1) and the surface water occurrence layer from Pekel et al. [2016]. Thus we obtained 7 images (one per image stack), each consisting of 56 predictor variables (Tab. 1).

5.3 Classification

Classification was performed using a machine learning algorithm which was trained using predictor variables as input data from the stacks of Landsat archive images. The covariates were derived from spectral indices in similar way as described in the previous subsection (Sec. 5.2) and represent physical environments along the continental Portuguese coast. In the study we experimented with CART and random forest classifiers, but the results which are presented in this thesis report were obtained with a random forest algorithm, as initial exploration, around the Sado Estuary indicated superior classification results. Nevertheless the CART classifier is readily deployable as classifier-algorithm in the developed classification framework.

Each of the seven 5-year composites was classified using Earth Engine’s built in supervised Random Forest classifier. The general workflow for classification was to collect training

data; instantiate a classifier; train the classifier using the training data; classify an image or feature collection; and estimate the classification error with independent validation data (Fig. 2). The sample points to train the classifier were interactively selected in Earth Engine using its geometry drawing tools in the JavaScript cloud text editor.

5.3.1 Predictor dataset

The choice of training data (or predictor data) is arguably the most difficult and critical part of the supervised classification process ([Canty, 2019]). The standard procedure is to select areas within several scenes which are representative of each class of interest. In this study the predictor data were calculated based upon a few hundred sample points (App. D) (± 400 ; 100 per class).

The sample points were selected interactively in Earth Engine using visual support from non-cloudy true (red, green blue) and false colour composites (nir, red, green). Here, especially the false colour composites were found to be useful because they help to locate heterogeneous patches in the landscape. Each sample point was labelled as one of the four target classes; water, sand, tidal-flat or other (App. B.2). Here, errors were tried to minimize by: 1) select the same number of training points per class; 2) use a minimum distance between training points, to avoid pseudo-replication and to increase generality of the training data; 3) select the centre of larger patches that are likely not mixed classes; 4) select a minimum of 30 points per class; 5) and, to represent the diversity present in each class. Subsequently a predictor dataset, consisting of 56 predictor variables (Tab. 1), was created by extracting surface reflection values at each of these sampling points, applying the same steps as described in subsection 5.2.

Individual selection of training points was preferred to stratified sampling. With stratified sampling an algorithm would randomly sample a certain amount of points from demarcated polygons. However, classification accuracy was found to be higher using manual interactive sampling.

Thus we obtained a predictor dataset (App. D) consisting of a property storing the class-label (water, sand, tidal flat or other) and properties storing predictor variables.

Half of this predictor data was retained for accuracy assessment. These comprise the so-called test data which are withheld from the training phase in order not to bias the subsequent evaluation. Hence, the training data partition was used to train the classifier, while the test partition was used for validation and accuracy assessment. For this study the predictor set was randomly split into a training and test dataset; for the final results respectively at 50:50 percent ratio, as training the algorithm was found relatively time-consuming, whilst initial exploration indicated that performance not necessary increased

Figure 4: Pair plot of median NDWI, mNDWI and AWEI values, separated by target class, altogether being a part of the predictor dataset

when more training data was included .

Figure 4 represents a pair plot of median NDWI, mNDWI and AWEI values, separated by target class, and part of the predictor dataset. It shows how each target-class can be distinguished by similarly characteristic spectral reflectance values. Here it was decided to include only NDWI, mNDWI and AWEI since they form the principal part of the predictor layer dataset.

5.3.2 Classifier

The classifier was constructed using Earth Engines *ee.Classifier* built in tool. The packages handles supervised classification in Earth Engine and contains various types of classifiers (*e.g.*, SVM, CART and random forest). In this study we used a random forest algorithm, while Murray et al. were followed in evaluating 10 decision trees for each pixel, in which a random sample equal to the square root of the number of predictors was considered at each split ([Murray et al., 2019]). Furthermore the resolution of the topography model classification analysis was restricted to areas less than 200-m in elevation, shallower than 75-m deep and within 5km of the coastline of continental Portugal. Here we used data from ETOPO1 Global Relief Model 32 to obtain information about bathymetry and topography. It was found that resolution of the model did not allow narrowing the range between depth and elevation further than -75-m to 200-m.

Deploying the trained algorithm, we thus obtained seven images, classified by pixel-level predictions into one of the four (water, sand, tidal-flat or other) classes (App. D).

The accuracy of the random forest algorithm was assessed by deploying it on the previously described test dataset. We found that overall accuracy was around 95%, with Cohen’s kappa coefficient of about 93%. Figure 5 shows the confusion matrix of the accuracy assessment.

5.4 Post-classification processing

Each classified image was post-processed using Earth Engines majority filter. This tool employs a moving window, with each central pixel assigned to the majority class of the pixels within the window; it replaces cells in a raster based on the majority of their contiguous neighbouring cells, at the scale of individual pixels. Effectively the filter reduces the ‘salt-and-pepper’ appearance typical of thematic maps generated by pixel-oriented classifiers (Canty [2019]). To obtain the final results the *pixelCount(x)*-filter was set at 25 pixels.

Thus we obtained seven majority-filtered maps of coastal continental Portugal at 30-m pixel resolution for set time-periods 1984-1989, 1989-1994, 1994-1999, 1999-2004, 2004-2009, 2009-2014, and 2014-2019, representing water, beaches, tidal-flats, and other types of land cover.

5.5 Beach evolution analysis

The majority-filtered classification maps were used to calculate and represent areas of sand gain and loss along the continental Portuguese coast between the first (1984-89) and last

Figure 5: Confusion matrix of random-forest classification on test dataset

(2014-19) time period; to calculate beach accretion and erosion per sediment cell over time; and, to extract shore and coastline information.

All final maps presented in this thesis report were obtained by applying a final mask (App. D) to reduce landward noise. This polygon mask was set out in the Earth Engine JavaScript IDE by visually interpreting the classification results with respect to false/true colour composites and geographical base-layers. Figure 6 shows the effect of this final mask for the Rio Formosa area south of Faro. The figure shows how the mask is reducing noise coming from urban areas being classified as sand. The mask is also effective in reducing noise coming from sand quarries, located relatively close to the coast, for example around the Sado estuary.

Finally all maps were processed in QGIS-3 (QGIS Development Team [2009]) to allow for adequate map visualization. All maps in this thesis report are shown in WGS 84:EPSG 4326 Projection, while spatial-context is provided by including base-layers from the Natural Earth Package.

Figure 6: Sand classifications with (yellow) and without (red) final mask, plotted on top of a true colour composite (2014-19)

5.5.1 Comparison of sandy areas between 1984-89 and 2014-19

The classified maps consist of numerical values (1,2,3 or 4) representing each of the classes. Using the classification map from the first and last time period considered, a new map was created, representing all possible class transitions in unique numerical values. This transition map was obtained by multiplying each pixel of the first classification by 10 and then adding the corresponding pixel value of the second classification to it. Subsequently sand loss(gain) was estimated from this transition image by summing class change of sand(water)-to-water(sand) and sand(tidal-flat)-to-tidal-flat(sand). Additionally a similar kind of map was calculated, now also including the sand(other)-to-other(sand) transition. Thus we created a map which represents areas of sand gain and loss along the continental Portuguese coast between 1984-89 and 2014-19.

Figure 7: Sediment cells along the continental Portuguese coast. Ponte Lira et al. [2016] was strictly followed in demarcation of these cells.

5.5.2 Evolution of beach area

For each of the seven time periods sand classifications were extracted from majority-filtered classification maps. After applying the previously described final beach mask to these extractions, the maps were assumed to represent beaches along the continental Portuguese coast. Thus we obtained seven maps representing beaches along the continental Portuguese coast.

Following Ponte Lira et al. [2016] the continental Portuguese coast was divided into ten sediment cells (Fig. 7). Subsequently the beach area was calculated using Earth Engines *ee.pixelArea()* tool for each of the cells in each of the seven time periods.

5.5.3 Shore and coastline polygons

The seven maps representing beaches along the continental Portuguese coast were also used to extract shore and coastline polygons. Therefore the format of this geospatial data was

converted from raster- to vector format using Earth Engine's raster-to-vector tool at 30-m scale. Multispectral satellite data is represented in raster format; each pixel representing the reflectance across multiple wavelengths within the electromagnetic spectrum. However, storing spatial details, such as edges of features, in this case beaches, is preferred in vector format, which is comprised of coded points (vertices) and lines. Earth Engine provides a built-in algorithm, which is able to convert the raster data of an image to vector data, based on homogeneous regions. However, immediate conversion from raster data to vector data will not lead to a desired beach polygon. Most multispectral Landsat images consist of pixels with a resolution of 30 x 30 meters and therefore the vector format beach polygons will have the same pixel size and the edges remain visibly jagged. Therefore the seven images representing beaches were resampled at 5-m using the bicubic resampling method. Finally these seven resampled images were converted to vector polygons using Earth Engine's *ee.reduceToVectors* tool. Figure 8 shows how resampling effectively increased representation of the beach courses by polygons. Thus we obtained seven polygon-collections, one for each of the seven time periods, representing resampled beaches along the continental Portuguese coast (App. D).

(a) TCC 2014-19; beach (resampled 5-m) in yellow (b) FCC 2014-19; beach (resampled 5-m) in yellow

(c) TCC 2014-19; beach 30-m black, while resampled beach (5-m) is shown in red

Figure 8: Effect of resampling 30-m to 5-m resolution around praia da Aberta Nova

5.6 Limitations

Despite the enormous potential of this automated beach classification method using long ranges of satellite data, it is necessary to acknowledge that there are important limitations

associated, that have already been described by other authors.

In the first place Wang et al. [2018] notes that there are significant tidal variations within each of the captured scenes. This will certainly affect our beach mapping process. In this study we try to avoid this problem by using dense stacks of Landsat imagery each containing five years of observations. In accordance with previous studies ([Murray et al., 2019, Luijendijk et al., 2018]), it is therefore assumed that by working with five year composites the tidal variations will be averaged out and can be neglected. In addition Wang et al. [2018] mentions that it is inevitable that the sensor of sun-synchronous satellite, such as Landsat, will only observe a portion of the full tidal range at any location, with less frequent observations at the extremely low and high tides. Therefore it can be assumed that the gross amount of observations are made at intermediate tidal levels, effectively reducing tidal bias.

Secondly, the magnitude of cross-shore excursion of the wave run-up potentially affects the image classification process. Luijendijk et al. [2018] have stressed that especially mild foreshore slopes, resulting in large horizontal tidal excursions hamper correct shoreline detection. However, since this study uses five-year composites, the seasonal variability in wave and beach characteristics will most likely be averaged out. Nevertheless the error magnitude could be significant, especially for gentle beach slopes. Therefore it is important to be aware of this assumption, which should also be studied further in future.

Thirdly, Luijendijk et al. [2018] mentions that high water content hampers correct shoreline detection. However, in this study, there is no distinction between ebb- and flood phases, and therefore the error should be cancelled out.

Fourthly, Wang et al. [2018] mentions that image data and algorithms are two factors that could affect the accuracy of tidal flat and low sandy area mapping. Working with Earth Engine is convenient since pre-processed imagery are readily available. However, working with pre-processed imagery may also cause flaws since errors in *e.g.*, atmospheric corrections may go unnoticed and will be more difficult to find.

Fifthly, Luijendijk et al. [2018] mentions there may be seaward offsets in detected shorelines. This may happen at sites with persistent swell conditions, where wave-induced foam due to wave breaking will introduce a seaward offset in detected shorelines. Hagenaars et al. [2017] presented a long-term, but local-scale satellite image analysis on shoreline trends, for a study site in north-western Netherlands, where the authors compared satellite data with ground-truth data. They found the accuracy of the satellite derived shoreline from moving average composite images to be of subpixel precision, about a pixel size, *i.e.*, 15-m for Landsat. Therefore Luijendijk et al. [2018] concluded that this accuracy of <15 m which was found by Hagenaars et al. [2017] for composite Landsat images, matches the required displacement of 15-m for reliable shoreline change classifications over the last 30 years.

Sixthly, the classification algorithms will likely miss darker coloured beaches since the algorithms are only trained on white to blonde coloured sandy beaches. However, as in mainland Portugal there are no dark beaches, this problem is not particularly relevant in this context.

Seventhly, no ground reference data were included in this study since their availability was limited in number of place and time. The training data were manually collected in Earth Engine. Murray et al. [2019] showed already that demarcation of tidal flats is tricky; there was only about 80% agreement among the experts in his study who labelled training data. Therefore it would most likely be more robust to use ground truth data to train the classifier algorithm and then deploy it on the imagery in Earth Engine. In the first place this would avoid some of the subjective decisions which had to be made in this study. Furthermore it would induce more randomness into the selection of training data, which will likely increase the diversity in samples among the classes. However, the quality of sampling sites could still be assessed by comparison to earlier work of Ponte Lira et al. [2016].

Finally, Luijendijk et al. [2018] also mentions that the reflectance signatures of sand and gravel beaches cannot be differentiated in the satellite imagery, as both materials originate from the same granular composites of finely divided rock.

Despite the limitations just described this thesis will elaborate (Ch. 6 and Ch. 7) on another specific issue using this approach: sensitivity of the classifier-algorithm to vegetation.

6 Results and evaluation

In this chapter we present beach extent evolution of continental Portugal over the last decades. Furthermore we will illustrate how the classification framework can be used to qualitatively analyse morphological beach-, shore and coastline evolution by giving local examples. Here results are qualitatively compared with previous research (Ponte Lira et al. [2016]; Pinto et al. [2017]); in so far as possible since their results were obtained using different methodologies and on different time frames.

6.1 Beach extent evolution

The sand classifications were extracted for each of the seven time periods, which allowed to study the evolution of continental Portuguese beach extent over the last decades. The beach images and polygons are accessible as Earth Engine asset (App. D) and can be explored in the Continental Portuguese Beach Change Explorer⁵.

⁵<https://florisrc.users.earthengine.app/view/ee-app-portuguese-beaches-v6>

Table 2 shows estimates of beach extent (m^2) along the continental Portuguese coast per each of the sediment cells (Fig. 7) for all the seven time periods. The lower two rows show the total area, one calculated by summing all cells, while the other is directly calculated in Earth Engine by calculating the area over all Portugal. The difference between these two estimates can be explained by the fact that there is some overlap between sediment cell 6 and 7 (Fig. 7), since it was decided to strictly follow Ponte Lira et al. [2016] in demarcation of the cells.

Table 2: Beach extent (m^2) per sediment cell for all seven time-periods

Area	1984-89	1989-94	1994-99	1999-04	2004-09	2009-14	2014-19
cell1a	7180399	6490276	5455330	5678569	4730889	4700365	4231042
cell1b	17513937	18898553	17116489	15652522	15376489	14814205	14939244
cell1c	10760007	11343995	9829340	9148176	9009728	8676989	8671156
cell2	4620180	4805517	3539406	3509762	3472584	3257423	3409226
cell3	4259075	4341615	3109750	3612176	3408808	3165835	3109384
cell4	4694895	5239735	4169580	3869387	3777972	3784629	3612550
cell5	12038152	11920611	10379258	10521122	10079369	8746243	8445673
cell6	3821818	4354188	3249104	3126583	3213290	2634855	2773812
cell7	4743239	5466970	4464539	4618066	3953202	3686249	3915809
cell8	20540796	19487567	17335732	16453713	15895412	12794381	12321166
Total	90172498	92349027	78648528	76190076	72917743	66261174	65429062
Total EE	89380831	91461260	77893853	75358339	72199121	65643508	64671307

These estimates are visualized in figure 9; a stacked bar plot, which also shows the percentage of each cell with respect to the total height of the y-axis. The table and figure show that beach extent has decreased for all sediment cells over the period of 1984-2019. Beach extent only slightly increased from the first (1984-89) to the second (1989-1994) period; since then it has been decreasing for all of following time periods. Sediment cell 8 has the strongest absolute decrease in beach extent, while also cell 1a, 1b and 5 decreased considerably. Compared to the size of sediment cells, absolute decrement in beach extent is most significant for cell 8 and 5 (Tab. 2; Fig. 7). However, when considering relative change in beach extent, cell 1a, 2 and 8 stand out in particular.

Although Ponte Lira et al. [2016] also found an overall trend of erosion (Ch. 3) some of

these results contrast with their coastline study. They found the strongest coastline retreat in cell 1b, 1a, 1c, 2 and 4, while only finding minor coastline retreat in cell 8. However, here it is important to note that it is problematic to compare beach extent to coastline evolution. Furthermore the classifier algorithm seems to be relatively sensitive to gentle changes in vegetation, which is illustrated in figure 12 and described in section 6.3. This sensitivity of the classifier-algorithm to vegetation appears to have a relatively large impact on beach extent estimations, since beach extent is dependent on both the shore and coastline. Some major differences in beach extent between the different time periods are in fact related to changes in coastal dune system, either through vegetation (Fig. 12), but also with their mobility, praia do Guincho (App. D; Continental Portuguese Beach Change Explorer). Therefore beach extent changes found in this study are especially problematic to compare with results from Ponte Lira et al. [2016]'s coastline study on a sediment cell level. Decrease in beach extent over 1984 - 2019 is in some places related to increased urbanisation, as illustrated in appendix C.2. Therefore it appears that overall continental Portuguese beaches are squeezing, mostly due to seaward propagation of coastlines, dependent increased vegetation or urbanisation and dune migration. Furthermore, especially for northern Portugal, the decrease in beach extent lines up with alluvial sources progressively weakening over the last few decades (Sec. 3.3, [Marinho et al., 2018]).

Figure 9: Beach extent of continental Portuguese beaches per sediment cell per time period. The stacked bars are annotated by the rounded percentage, relative to the length of y-axis.

6.2 Morphodynamics: Sado estuary

Here we present a local example of how the classification framework can be used to study morphodynamics of sandy areas in the coastal zone. The maps in figure 10 show the evolution of tidal-ebb bars and beaches in the south-western part of the tidal inlet of the Sado estuary. This figure shows how, over the last 35 years, tidal-ebb bars migrate, grow, disappear and arise. Furthermore it shows how there is gradual but strong accretion on the northern tip of this Troia sand spit. Here there is qualitative accordance with Ponte Lira et al. [2016]. This figure is an example of how the beach classification framework can be used to study the morphodynamics of tidal-ebb sand bars and beaches.

Qualitative visual assessment shows that overall accuracy appears to be around one pixel; near shores of either beaches and tidal-ebb islands, there are some areas which you would expect to be classified as sand, but are classified differently. Furthermore, sub-figure (e-

to-f) show how the tidal-ebb bar is only recognized by the classifier-algorithm in subfigure (f). These areas were all classified as tidal-flat (App. D; RF-classifications). Most likely this is explained by the fact that 53/56 predictor variables (Tab. 1) where the algorithm was trained on, are spectral indices with high sensitivity to wetness (Sec. 4.4). Most likely, wetness has therefore a strong impact on the predictions of classifier-algorithm.

(a) 1984-89

(b) 1989-94

(c) 1994-99

(d) 1999-2004

(e) 2004-09

(f) 2009-2014

(g) 2014-19

Figure 10: Migrating tidal-ebb sandbars at the tidal inlet of the Sado estuary over 1984-2019. Each sub-figure shows one of the seven time-periods. Sand classifications for each of the time-periods are distinguished by colour, following the colour palette used in the Continental Portuguese Beach Change Explorer.

6.3 Maps of change in beaches between 1984-89 and 2014-19

The classified maps were also used to estimate and show sand gain- and loss along the continental Portuguese coast between the first (1984-89) and last (2014-19) time period. The sand gain- and loss maps for all the coast of continental Portugal are available as Earth Engine asset (App. D) and can be explored in the Continental Portuguese Beach Change Explorer⁶.

Figure 11 shows an example of these maps, around Ria Formosa, at Praia da Culatra in the Algarve. The figure is composed of two (1984-89; 2014-19) true colour composites (red, green blue), showing the tidal inlet in this area during those two time periods, while a third map also shows an overlay of areas representing sand gain and loss between those time periods. This figure represents sand gain(loss) as the sum of the transition from water(sand) to sand(water) and from tidal-flat(sand) to sand(tidal-flat). Here it is important to note that the transition from other(sand) to sand(other) is not included in the analysis. Due to the scope of this project all other class transitions *e.g.*, water(tidal-flat) to tidal-flat(water) were not considered in this study.

It shows that between 1984-89 and 2014-19 there has been beach accretion for both Praia da Culatra and da Armonamar on the seaside of the Armona inlet, while there has been some erosion on the landward side of the inlet. Using Earth Engine's *ee.pixelArea()* tool the net-sand gain in this area can be estimated around 647429 m². However, since the other(sand) to sand(other) transitions is not included, this sand gain is assumed to have happened only with respect to the beach that remained unchanged; the coastline is assumed to have been constant. The evolution and growth of this Culatra island is in qualitative accordance with a previous study from Garcia et al. [2002].

⁶<https://florisrc.users.earthengine.app/view/ee-app-portuguese-beaches-v6>

(a) TCC 1984-19

(b) TCC 2014-19

(c) TCC 2014-19; unchanged sand in yellow, gained sand in green and lost sand in red

Figure 11: Change of beaches between 1984-89 and 2014-19, south of Faro

The other(sand) to sand(other) class transitions were initially excluded because the classification algorithm is sensitive to gentle changes in vegetation. Figure C.1 in appendix C, shows the same area, but now also including this other(sand) to sand(other) transition. It is an example of sensitivity of the classifier-algorithm to changes in vegetation and migrating

dunes. This sensitivity is also clearly illustrated in figure (Fig. 12). The figure is composed of three maps at the tidal inlet of Praia da ilha Deserta, also around Ria Formosa. The first two maps show true colour composites of 1984-89 and 2014-19 respectively, while the third map represents an overlay of the two sand classifications for those two periods. The figure shows that there appear only to be minor changes in vegetation (subfigure a and b), especially in the north-eastern area, while the difference in area which is classified as beach is relatively large.

(a) TCC 1984-89

(b) TCC 2014-19

(c) TCC 2014-19; beach 1984-89 in dark-blue, beach 2014-19 in red

Figure 12: Difference in areas classified as beach between the first and last time period, south of Faro at the Farol tidal inlet, due to small changes in vegetation

6.4 Shore and coastline visualization

The seven beach maps of the continental Portuguese coast were also used to extract polygons, which can be used to study shore and coastline evolution. The shore and coastlines were extracted for all the seven time periods, along the whole continental Portuguese coastline, are available as Earth Engine asset (App. D and can be explored in the Continental Portuguese Beach Change Explorer⁷.

Here we present a local example (Fig. 13), around the northern jetty of the tidal inlet of the Aveiro lagoon. The figure shows the long beach stretches of Praia de Jacinto gradually migrated seaward since 1984, over the seven time periods, until present. These accretional trends were also observed by Ponte Lira et al. [2016] and can be explained by the presence of the Aveiro jetties. These jetties are significant obstacles to littoral drift, which is north-south along the western coast of Portugal (Sec. 3.3).

Figure 13 also shows how the estimated shoreline is located landward off the visible water/land interface that is portrayed in the figure. However, since the shoreline is defined as the wet- and dry beach boundary (Sec. 4.1), the difference can be assumed to be relatively small. The classifier-algorithm was mostly trained on predictor variables (53/56; Tab. 1) calculated from spectral indices which are especially useful to distinguish in water-land boundaries, since they exploiting the infrared bands (Sec. 4.4). This makes the algorithm particularly sensitive to water content. Therefore, the classification algorithm defines shoreline boundaries presumably at the upper limit of the swash-zone, the boundary between wet- and dry-beach, of intermediate (composite) tide-levels (Sec. 5.3). However, surf and swash zones will still be visible in the true colour composite as vague-blue to yellowish pixels. This landward-off estimation of shorelines appears to be larger along the continental Portuguese west coast, where the wave climate is more intense (Sec. 3.3).

Furthermore, according to figure 8 and 13, the classification algorithm defines the coastline at about the first pixel with increased vegetation, presumably relatively close to the foredune toe. However, visual comparison with [Ponte Lira et al., 2016] around the Faro-Olhão inlet (Fig. 12) indicates that the classifier algorithm demarcates the coastline more landward than the foredune-toe identified by Ponte Lira et al. [2016]. Most likely, the relatively small increase in vegetation at exactly the foredune toe is not sufficient to trigger the classifier-algorithm to classify this landcover as non-beach. Therefore coastline demarcation is more land-inward, compared to Ponte Lira et al. [2016], presumably around the middle of the foredune, following Carapuço et al. [2016]’s definition.

⁷<https://florisrc.users.earthengine.app/view/ee-app-portuguese-beaches-v6>

(a) TCC 1984-89; shore- coastline 1984-19 in blue (b) TCC 2014-19; shore- coastline 2014-19 in red

(c) TCC 2019-19; shore and coastlines for seven time periods, separated by colour

Figure 13: Shore and coastline evolution between 1984 - 2019 around the Aveiro harbour jetty

7 Discussion

7.1 Google Earth Engine

The Earth Engine is a promising platform to process geospatial data due to its computational power and versatility. In this study for example, we were able to filter, process and classify 8734 Landsat images into seven classified maps in just about one hour. Furthermore, Earth Engine already contains a rich set of freely available and pre-processed data, and this is only expected to grow in the near future. Then, Earth Engine is easily accessible for all users, even for those who do not have high-level programming skills or access to powerful computers. The online JavaScript editor is guided by several easy to follow tutorials, with clear examples from some high-impact studies. The overall experience of working with Earth Engine in this JavaScript IDE is light, and would be within reach for everyone with some motivation to learn basic programming skills.

The Python API is more complex to set up. This Python API is not equally transparent; for example, there is no possibility for map visualization without processing. However, the Python API is definitely promising for the more advanced users, by offering more freedom in customization. It may be useful in particular for more advanced studies with large amounts of processing and (export-)results. In this study it was therefore found most productive to explore the data sets and tools using the cloud JavaScript IDE, while developing the final framework in the Python API.

The Earth Engine API includes many powerful tools, including a wide range of machine learning algorithms, which are relatively easy to implement (Sec. 4.3). However, applying tools which are not provided by Earth Engine's API remains difficult since Earth Engine only works efficiently with Earth Engine objects (Sec. 4.3). Furthermore, the available tools can only be customized within the limits of what Earth Engine provides. Here, it would have been promising to implement a XGBoost- instead of a random forest algorithm (Sec. 4.5; Georganos et al. [2018]), but unfortunately this algorithm is not yet available in Earth Engine. Earth Engine also does not include any feature engineering tools. Feature engineering is a very common and useful practice in machine learning studies, which determines which predictor variables are most significant in the prediction of the target variable. This information is then used for optimization of the classifier algorithm. Unfortunately feature engineering is currently in Earth Engine only possible by trial-and-error, which is too fuzzy and time-consuming when several predictor variables are included in the study.

Another caveat is related to the fact that Earth Engine does not yet incorporate an algorithm to reduce pixels to vectors by the centre of a pixel. The only available reduce-to-vector algorithm follows the borders of pixels and therefore the polygons remain visibly

jagged (Fig. 8). Even when image is resampled to smaller scale (Fig. 8) the same problem arises, although substantially hampered.

Earth Engine also does not allow to completely format maps according to common map standards. For example, it requires advanced programming skills to develop and include a north arrow, legend and scale-bar. Therefore, most Earth Engine processing has to be finalized in more conventional GIS software, which then suddenly involves labour-intensive exporting of several layers from Earth Engine. This is an example of a more fundamental issue of Earth Engine. Working with Earth Engine is straightforward and simple until you leave the beaten track; then, suddenly high level programming skills are required with in-depth knowledge of JavaScript language.

Finally, especially with respect to coastal studies, Earth Engine is limited by the fact that requesting metadata of an image stops the rest of processing (Sec. 4.3). It is therefore, for example, complex to include tidal corrections, in particularly when working with composite images, on spatially larger scales (generally when the area is bigger than 1 Landsat image). In this study it was, for example, attempted to filter (by NDWI index) the image collections, prior to compositing, in order to sort out the extremely high and low tides. However, this filtering incorporated an image-to-array conversion, which was too computationally demanding for areas bigger than one Landsat image.

7.2 Evolution of Portuguese beaches

7.2.1 Classification accuracy

In this study we used a supervised machine learning algorithm to classify beaches along the continental Portuguese coast. The final results were obtained by applying a trained random forest algorithm to classify seven time periods, in total consisting of 8734 Landsat images. The algorithm was trained by interactive collection of training data (about 400 samples) in Earth Engine's JavaScript IDE. The overall accuracy was about 93% (Fig. 5), which is relatively high considering the complex coastal environments along the continental Portuguese coast. However, here it is important to note that no ground-truth data were used to train and test the accuracy of this classifier algorithm. Murray et al. [2019] already showed how complex interactive collection of training data is (Sec. 5.6), while also Canty [2019] notes that this is the most difficult and critical part of supervised classification process.

Overall, absence of ground-truth data is presumably the most important limitation of this study, as training data had to be sampled subjectively, without any reference to objective field data. Nevertheless, Ponte Lira et al. [2016]'s study allowed to visually validate the sampling points and assess the accuracy to some extent. However, as a result of the absence

of objective ground-truth data, we could not assess the accuracy of shore and coastline extraction objectively; we were only able to assess accuracy by visual inspection. This examination indicated that classification errors regarding the shoreline were relatively small, mostly around pixel-level. In some areas, especially on the western coast of continental Portugal, this landward offset appeared to be larger (Fig. 13), up to about 4 pixels. However, this offset is presumably related to higher setup, due to larger waves (Sec. 3.3) that moist the beach face. Therefore it seems that, due to its water content, the classifier algorithm correctly classifies these areas other than dry-beach. Figure 4 shows how the median spectral indices of sand have a clear peak; especially NDWI and mNDWI are both particularly distinct from tidal-flats and water. Presumably, sensitivity of the classifier algorithm to water-content effectively causes the algorithm to demarcate the shoreline exactly at the first pixel with water-content, which would generally be the upper limit of the swash-zone. Therefore accuracy in shoreline demarcation can be assumed to be around sub-pixel to pixel level (15-30m). On the other hand, coastline demarcation appears to be more dynamic and problematic, since gentle changes in vegetation cause relatively large shifts in sand classification (Fig. 12). Generally it appears that the coastline is demarcated by the classifier algorithm at the central-foredune (following Carapuço et al. [2016]; Fig. 8, 13, 12). Clear coastline demarcation is often also hindered in urban areas by confusion of buildings with sand. Figure 4 provides the physical framework to explain that spectral indices for "sand" and "other" classes often overlap. Therefore it is often problematic to extract beaches and especially the coastline in coastal areas with high levels of urbanisation, like Costa de Caparica.

7.2.2 Beach, shore and coastline evolution

The classifier algorithm was eventually used to study beach evolution over the seven time periods. Due to (miss-)classifications of sand quarries and buildings more land-inward it was necessary to interactively mask out all sand-classifications outside the coastal barrier. Then it was assumed that the remaining sand classification would represent the continental Portuguese beaches. However, there are still some miss-classifications included, particularly of buildings, for example, around Costa de Caparica and the coastal urban areas in the Algarve. Nevertheless the seven maps appear to be useful to study coastal morphodynamics on the multi-annual time scale: it was shown that they can be used to track tidal-ebb delta islands (Fig. 10); visualize beach accretion; track shore and coastline (Fig. 13); and, identify the most dynamic areas of the last 35 years (Fig. 11). Here it was found that our results are generally in accordance with earlier studies. For examples, areas with strong beach accretion, like the Troia sand pit, the Armona inlet, and the Aveiro jetties were also

identified by Ponte Lira et al. [2016] as areas of coastline accretion. Likewise we also found that the shoreline (1984-89 versus 2014-19) is predominantly eroding in central- to north-Portugal; sectors such as Esposende-Viana do Castelo, Toreirra-Porto and Aveiro-Palheiros da Torcha are all characterized by retreating shorelines. Further south, there is accretion around Figuera da Foz, but this pattern gradually changes to erosion southwards, towards Nazaré.⁸ These patterns are in accordance with what Ponte Lira et al. [2016] characterized as the most relevant beach erosion issues (Sec. 3.3). Likewise we also find that the shoreline is retreating in cell 8 (Fig.7), although the rates of change do not appear to be so dramatic as found by Ponte Lira et al. [2016]. Shoreline retreat in north-Portugal is most likely associated to progressively weakening of alluvial sources (Sec. 3.3), while here accretion can mostly be related to groynes, effectively trapping north-south alongshore transport (Sec. 3.3). Most of the highly dynamic areas, like Ria Formosa, (Fig. 11) are areas which were characterized by Pinto et al. [2017] for intense beach nourishment during the last decades (Sec. 3.3), while coastal structures were (already) built ([Garcia et al., 2002]).

In this study it was found that, during the last 35 years, beaches of continental Portugal squeezed, from about 90 km² to 65 km² (Fig. 9; Tab. 2). We found that for all different sediment cells beach extent is decreasing. These results are in accordance with Ponte Lira et al. [2016] for sediment cell 1a, 1b, 1b, but contrast with their assessment for cell 8. However, our study indicates that surface beach decrement appears to be mainly dependent upon propagation of the coastline, due to increased urbanisation (*e.g.*, Aveiro sand pit, App. C.2), increasing vegetation (*e.g.*, Culatra island; Praia North, Nazaré) or mobility of dunes (praia do Guincho). This decrement in dry-beach extent due to propagation of the coastline is also illustrated by the fact that there is a net-gain of about 0.48 km² in beach extent when the class transition from other(sand) to sand(other) is not considered in the calculation (Sec. 5.4).

7.3 Overall evaluation of framework

The classification framework can be useful in studying coastal morphodynamics on multi-annual to decadal time scale, especially on spatially larger scales (meso- to macro scale). Overall, accuracy appears to be sufficient to study evolution of beaches, make rough estimates about change in beach surface and appears to be promising for shoreline extraction, *i.e.*, boundary wet- and dry-beach. Considering large areas (*e.g.* continental Portugal) quantification of change in beach surface extent are rough estimates, since the classifier algorithm

⁸See sand gain/loss layer at: <https://florisrc.users.earthengine.app/view/ee-app-portuguese-beaches->

is sensitive to small changes in vegetation and struggles with urban areas and migrating dunes, altogether effectively causing large shifts in beach surface extent. However, considering smaller study areas, where one is familiar with the performance of the algorithm, estimates may be relatively accurate (Fig. 11).

Regarding shoreline extraction it may be more effective to apply the approach of either Luijendijk et al. [2018] and Vos et al. [2019]. Implementing thresholding algorithms, which consider just one spectral index (Sec. 4.1, would allow for easier tidal corrections and facilitates convenient shoreline extraction, while having high accuracy (sub-pixel; 15-m for Landsat) at the same time. However, here we also studied extent and trajectories of beaches, wherefore it was required to use a classifier algorithm. Nevertheless results would likely be improved if the sea/beach boundary would be determined by thresholding algorithms.

8 Recommendations and outlook

For multiple reasons it would be fruitful to include ground-truth data in any improvement of this the study. In the first place this would allow to go beyond the confusion matrix accuracy assessment. At this stage all data (training, testing and target) are coming from the same source, wherefore it is problematic to compare. Including ground-truth data would allow for error estimation of, for example, the shoreline extraction.

Furthermore it could be promising to extract shorelines with thresholding algorithms (Vos et al. [2019]; [Luijendijk et al., 2018]), instead of deriving them from classifier algorithms. This could allow for tidal corrections, while sufficiently high accuracy of shoreline mapping (about 15m with Landsat) is retained.

In the current framework it is difficult to quantify shore and coastline evolution. Initially it was tried to study shore and coastline by ingesting the beach-polygons into GIS software, where shore and coastlines could be separated, allowing for shoreline analysis with, for example, the DSAS-tool(Himmelstoss et al. [2018]). However, due to presence of several small beaches and the extensive study area, it was found too labour intensive to manually separate shore and coastlines in every beach-polygon. Instead it would be more promising to further analyse the shore and coastline evolution from a local environment by calculating intersection with cross-shore transects for the different beach polygons (Luijendijk et al. [2018]).

We found that in the current framework, the classifier algorithm is especially sensitive to gentle changes in vegetation, effectively causing high variation in beach extent estimation. To increase these estimates of beach extent, it could be interesting to study whether the shore-dune boundary (foredune-toe) can be extracted more consistently with thresholding

algorithms instead of being deduced from classifier algorithms. In order to assess where coastlines are extracted by the classifier-algorithm it would be useful to make a cross-shore profile to study the gradient in spectral signatures across the beach. Furthermore, it would also be beneficial to study how vegetation in the dunes evolved during the last decades, for example, by using the NDVI-index.

Beach morphodynamics may also be reflect the large scale atmospheric patterns that were found to drive the inter-annual wave variability along the continental Portuguese coast (Marraccini [2015]); the atmosphere might have a fundamental secondary driver capacity on beach evolution. Here we presented a continuous dataset of beach extent and its dynamics since 1984. It would therefore be promising to study whether the dynamics and evolution of continental Portuguese beaches can be related to atmosphere over the North Atlantic ocean.

In this study we decided to train the classifier algorithm in distinguishing four classes (water, tidal-flat, sand and other). However, due to time limitations, almost no attention was paid to optimizing a classifier algorithm trained to distinguish between, for example, three or five classes. Most likely significant improvements in results can be obtained with feature engineering (Ch. 7) of spectral indices, predictor variables and target classes. It might, for example, be beneficial to add a class particularly dedicated to represent dunes.

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A Remote sensing

Table A.1: Commonly used remote sensing sensors in surface water detection (Huang et al. [2018]).

Category	Satellite/sensor	Bands	Spatial resolution (m)	Temporal resolution (day)	Data availability
Coarse >200m	NOAA/AVHRR	5	1100	0.5	1978
	MODIS	36	250-1000	0.5	1999
	Suomi NPP-VHRS	22	375-750	0.5	2012-
	MERIS	15	300	3	2002-12
	Sentinel-3 OLCI	21	300	2	2016-
Medium 5-200m	Landsat	4-9	15-80	16	1972-
	SPOT	4-5	2.5-20	26	1986-
	Aster	14	15-90	16	1999-
	Sentinel-2 MSI	13	10-60	5	2015-
	High <5m	IKONOS	5	1-4	1.5-3
QuickBird		5	0.61-2.24	2.7	2001
WorldView		4-17	0.31-2.40	1-4	2007-
RapidEye		5	5	1-5.5.	2008-
ZY-3		4	2.1-5.8	5	2012-
GF-1/GF-2		5	1-16	4-5	2013-

Table A.2: General information about different Landsat missions (source: NASA)

Mission	Operating	Sensor	Bands	Resolution (m)	Revisit (days)
Landsat-1	1972-1978	RBV/MSS	7	80	18
Landsat-2	1975-1983	RBV/MSS	7	80	18
Landsat-3	1978-1983	RBV/MSS	7	40/80	18
Landsat-4	1982-1993	MSS/TM	7	80/30	16
Landsat-5	1984-2013	MSS/TM	7	80/30	16
Landsat-6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Landsat-7	1999-present	ETM+	8	30	16
Landsat-8	2013-present	OLI/TIRS	11	30/15/100	16

B Google Earth Engine IDE

Figure B.1: The interactive development environment of Google Earth Engine. It shows a Landsat image in the interactive display with its properties in the console on the right-upper side.

Figure B.2: Interactive demarcation and labelling of sampling points in the Earth Engine cloud editor. These sampling points (about 400 in total) were used to generate a predictor data set.

C Sand classifications

(a) TCC 1984-89

(b) TCC 2014-19

(c) TCC 2014-19; unchanged sand in yellow, gained sand in green and lost sand in red

Figure C.1: Change of beaches between 1984-89 and 2014-19, south of Faro at the Armona inlet. Here it is important to note that the sand(other) to other(sand) is now in the change analysis.

(a) TCC 1984-89

(b) TCC 2014-19

(c) TCC 2014-19; beach 1984-89 in blue; beach 2014-19 in red

Figure C.2: Effect of urbanisation on surface beach extent at the Aveiro sand pit

D Developed Earth Engine assets

1. Sampling points: <https://code.earthengine.google.com/80c8db7874c0d7e13bb4e1677fa02779>

2. Predictor dataset: *ee.FeatureCollection('users/florisrc/predictorSetV1')*
3. Final beach mask: *ee.FeatureCollection('users/florisrc/finalBeachMask')*
4. Composites
 - (a) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/vis_1984-01-01_1989-01-01')*
 - (b) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/vis_1989-01-01_1994-01-01')*
 - (c) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/vis_1994-01-01_1999-01-01')*
 - (d) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/vis_1999-01-01_2004-01-01')*
 - (e) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/vis_2004-01-01_2009-01-01')*
 - (f) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/vis_2009-01-01_2014-01-01')*
 - (g) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/vis_2014-01-01_2019-01-01')*
5. Classified maps
 - (a) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_rf_1984-01-01_1989-01-01')*
 - (b) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_rf_1989-01-01_1994-01-01')*
 - (c) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_rf_1994-01-01_1999-01-01')*
 - (d) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_rf_1999-01-01_2004-01-01')*
 - (e) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_rf_2004-01-01_2009-01-01')*
 - (f) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_rf_2009-01-01_2014-01-01')*
 - (g) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_rf_2014-01-01_2019-01-01')*
6. Extracted beaches
 - (a) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_beachImage_1984-01-01_1989-01-01')*
 - (b) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_beachImage_1989-01-01_1994-01-01')*
 - (c) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_beachImage_1994-01-01_1999-01-01')*
 - (d) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_beachImage_1999-01-01_2004-01-01')*
 - (e) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_beachImage_2004-01-01_2009-01-01')*
 - (f) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_beachImage_2009-01-01_2014-01-01')*
 - (g) *ee.Image('users/florisrc/clas_beachImage_2014-01-01_2019-01-01')*
7. Resampled extracted beaches
 - (a) *ee.FeatureCollection('users/florisrc/beach_resampled_fc_1984-1989')*
 - (b) *ee.FeatureCollection('users/florisrc/beach_resampled_fc_1989-1994')*
 - (c) *ee.FeatureCollection('users/florisrc/beach_resampled_fc_1994-1999')*
 - (d) *ee.FeatureCollection('users/florisrc/beach_resampled_fc_1999-2004')*

- (e) *ee.FeatureCollection('users/florisrc/beach_resampled_fc_2004-2009')*
 - (f) *ee.FeatureCollection('users/florisrc/beach_resampled_fc_2009-2014')*
 - (g) *ee.FeatureCollection('users/florisrc/beach_resampled_fc_2014-2019')*
8. Change map (1984-89 vs 2014-19): *ee.Image('users/florisrc/change1984vs2014')*
 9. Change map complete (1984-89 vs 2014-19): *ee.Image('users/florisrc/change1984vs2014complete')*
 10. Mosaic shore and coastlines: *ee.Image('users/florisrc/mosaicShoreAndCoastLines')*